

Current and Future Scenario of Experimental Research Involving Quantum Networks and Telecommunications

Armando Nolasco Pinto, Nuno Alexandre Peixoto Silva, Tereza Cristina de Brito Carvalho, Joberto S. B. Martins, Cristiano Bonato Both and Antônio Jorge Gomes Abelém

Abstract

This technical report presents the slides and additional technical information concerning the round table addressing the topic of *Current and Future Scenario of Experimental Research Involving Quantum Networks and Telecommunications*.

The round table presentations and technical discussions occurred during the 13o Future Internet Research and Experimentation Workshop (WPEIF) held at the XL Brazilian Symposium on Computer Networks and Distributed Systems, Fortaleza - CE, May 27th, 2022 (<https://sbrc2022.sbc.org.br/en/xiii-workshop-de-pesquisa-experimental-da-internet-do-futuro-wpeif-2022/>).

This document is a technical report of the project SLICING FUTURE INTERNET INFRASTRUCTURES numbered SFI2 TR01/2022.

Index Terms

Experimental Networks, Quantum Networks, Network Slicing, Telecommunications.

1 ABSTRACT - ROUND TABLE PRESENTATION

The Internet is one of the pillars of the information age, a central component of the fourth industrial revolution, and the foundation for new applications and services that will impact individuals, businesses, and society. Technological evolution, in turn, also influences the Internet, which, in a short time, will be very different from its current structure.

The next frontier is the Internet of Everything (IoE) which will allow a continuous and real-time connection between things, people, and processes through a constant data flow. The IoE will encompass the Internet of Things (IoT), the Internet of People (IoP), the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), and the Tactile Internet.

This scenario requires a flexible network capable of supporting the different needs of current and future IoE applications. For this, the research community is turning to the networks of the future involving initiatives such as the Next Generation Internet (NGI) in Europe and Tomorrow's Internet Project in the United States, in addition to several other actions such as the next generation of mobile telecommunications networks for 2030, 6G. In Brazil, projects such as FIBRE [1], FIWARE, FUTEBOL [2], 5GINFIRE [3], NECOS [4], CloudNEXT and SFI2 [5] [6], carried out in collaborations between Europe and Brazil, create conditions to experiment with different scenarios of networks and applications with a focus on the future.

-
- *Armando Nolasco Pinto is with Instituto de Telecomunicações de Aveiro , Portugal.*
 - *Nuno Alexandre Peixoto Silva is with Instituto de Telecomunicações de Aveiro , Portugal.*
 - *Tereza Cristina de Brito Carvalho is with Universidade de São Paulo (USP), Brazil. E-mail: terezacarvalho@usp.br*
 - *Joberto S. B. Martins is with Salvador University - UNIFACS, Brazil. E-mail: joberto.martins@unifacs.br*
 - *Cristiano Bonato Both is with Universidade do Vale dos Sinos (UNISINOS), Brazil. E-mail: cbboth@unisinis.br*
 - *Antônio Jorge Abelém is with Universidade Federal do Pará (UFPA), Brazil. E-mail: abelem@ufpa.br*

Several technologies will enable this revolution, such as cloud, fog, and edge computing, software-defined networks, network function virtualization, network virtualization and slicing, software-defined infrastructure, advanced optical communications, and software-defined radios. In addition to these technologies, various techniques of artificial intelligence, engineering, and data science will be the basis for future infrastructure, networks, and applications.

In its thirteenth edition, the Future Internet Experimental Research Workshop (WPEIF) aims to consolidate discussions and exchanges of information, knowledge, and experiences on experimental research related to the applications and networks of the future, aiming to create the next generation of networks of tomorrow.

By discussing the topic *Current and Future Scenario of Experimental Research Involving Quantum Networks and Telecommunications* with the computer networks and distributed systems community, the Workshop seeks to be a beacon in this area of research that contains numerous challenges and opportunities.

2 ROUND-TABLE SLIDES

XIII Workshop de Pesquisa Experimental da Internet do Futuro (WPEIF 2022)

SF12 - SLICING FUTURE INTERNET INFRASTRUCTURES MULTIINSTITUTIONAL COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH PROJECT

SF12 Project Summary

Tereza Cristina de Carvalho
Joberto S. B. Martins

Fig. 1.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

-- > **SF12 links:**

- SF12: <https://sites.google.com/view/sfi2/home>
- Deliverables: <https://sites.google.com/view/sfi2/home/deliverables>

Agenda

- SF12 objectives
- Context and strategy
- SF12 status

SF12 project: 01/03/2021 a 28/02/2026

Fig. 2.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Objectives

SFI2 research's objective is to develop a network slicing solution that provides orchestration and allocation of resources in multi-domain experimentation network infrastructures.

Machine learning techniques will assist in slicing in multi-domain network infrastructures to provide near-automatic resource identification and allocation.

Fig. 3.

-- > ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:

Context

In experimental network infrastructures (testbeds) new technologies are added to the academic Internet in a controlled manner, allowing the experimentation of new disruptive protocols and architectures

There are currently several infrastructures for experimentation in Brazil linked to SDN concepts, NFV, cloud computing, and 5G (FIBRE, NECOS, 5GINFIRE, FUTEBOL, CloudNEXT, FIWARE)

SFI2 Project aims to integrate, to some extent, these experimental facilities in Brazil

Fig. 4.

-- > ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:

SFI2 Strategy

From the architectural and deployment point of view, try to incorporate previous results obtained by other experimental network research projects

- FIBRE research network in Brazil (18 islands)
- NECOS project outcomes

Project planning includes defining new requirements for wide-scale slicing in the context of experimental networks

- Uses cases are being developed currently with this specific objective
- Uses cases will guide the SFI2 specific architecture proposal
- Good results and good practices from NECOS project architecture and deployment will be considered

Fig. 5.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Use Cases

Fig. 6.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Use Case 1 SLICING ORCHESTRATION USING MACHINE LEARNING

- The objective of Use Case 1 (UC1) is to use machine learning to orchestrate network slicing. The SFI2 architecture, derived from the NECOS project architecture, supports the Use Case deployment. Architectural components must be explicit about embedding machine learning (ML) techniques and methods in the SFI2 architecture. In this context, the proposition is to **extend the NECOS architecture** for explicitly deal with **machine learning techniques** for **slice orchestration** and **other phases of the network slicing life-cycle**.

- UC1 Setup:
 - Backbone: FIBRE Backbone
 - Docker/Kubernetes based
 - Monitoring: CASANDRA/Prometheus
 - Pseudo-Domains: FIBRE islands: UFU, UFG, UFPA, USP
- Partners: UFU, UFPA, UFV, UFPE and UNIFACS

Fig. 7.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Use Case 2

ULTRA RELIABLE LOW LATENCY COMMUNICATION

SF12

- Use case 2 aims to provide **reliable and low latency communication for Industry 4.0 and Smart City** environments:
 - Drone flight control
 - Remote operation of machinery
 - Virtual and augmented reality, games
- The main research challenge is the **orchestration of different types of networks**, using machine learning and network virtualization techniques, while keeping tight **QoS requirements**. Key enablers are:
 - Deep reinforcement learning
 - Time-sensitive networking
 - In-band telemetry
- Partners: UFMG, ITA

Fig. 8.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Use Case 3 5G Slicing

- The main objective of Use Case 3 (UC3) is to study the use of **slicing in 5G networks** and to propose and evaluate mechanisms that guarantee the **requirements of different slices** in a **dynamic environment**.
- UC3 Current Actions
 - Design, deploy, and evaluation of **5G Core and O-RAN RIC support for 5G slicing**
 - System modeling and formalization of **URLLC guarantees**
- Partners: UFRJ, UFG, UNISINOS, UFU, UFMG, and UFRGS

Fig. 9.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Use Case 4

ENERGY-EFFICIENT SLICING

- The main objective of Use Case 4 (UC4) is to introduce slicing as a new enabler supporting the **deployment of efficient distributed network infrastructures** while enforcing energy efficiency in the slicing **3GPP life-cycle** phases of **preparation, commissioning, operation, and decommissioning**
- UC4 Slicing Premises:
 - **Energy Efficiency** requirements and policies are essential criteria for **slicing**
 - UC4 approach for slice's requirement specification uses an **intent-based** style
 - The UC4 slicing approach fosters **renewable energy** use (green computing)
- Partners: USP, UFG, IFSP, UFPE, UNIFACS and PUC-RS

Fig. 10.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

- Use case 1 homepage: <https://sites.google.com/view/sfi2/home/sfi2-use-case-1-machine-learning-bas>

SF12 TEAM AND SUPPORT (by March 28th, 2020)

- **Fifteen (15) Brazilian research institutions:**

- 24 researchers directly involved
- One (1) PosDoc
- One (1) PhD student
- Three (3) master students

- **Networking and Technical support:**

- RNP – Rede Nacional de Pesquisa
- FIBRE project

Fig. 11.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Discussion

<https://sites.google.com/view/sfi2/home>

Fig. 12.

-- > **PAPER TEXT EXTRACT:**

PORVIR-5G
PROGRAMMABILITY, ORCHESTRATION AND VIRTUALIZATION

Cenário atual e futuro da pesquisa experimental envolvendo as redes quânticas e telecomunicações

Cristiano Bonato Both
cbboth@unisinis.br

Projeto financiado através da Cooperação Científica e Tecnológica entre FAPESP, MCTIC e CGI - Projeto de Pesquisa Temático. Processo nº 2020/05182-3.

UFMG UNICAMP UNISINOS UFRGS UFES

Fig. 13.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Visão geral

PORVIR-5G: Programabilidade, ORquestração e VIRTualização de Redes em 5G

Pesquisador responsável: José Marcos Silva Nogueira

Instituição sede: Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais (Instituto de Ciências Exatas)

Instituições participantes:

- Universidade Federal do Espírito Santo
- Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul
- Universidade do Vale do Rio dos Sinos
- Universidade Estadual de Campinas
- Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais

2

Fig. 14.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Competências das equipes

Fig. 15.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Objetivos Gerais

Objetivo 1

Conceber uma arquitetura aberta que ofereça **programabilidade** e **orquestração** para **fatiamento** de rede, com consistência semântica na expressividade, perpassando:

- parâmetros e funcionalidades nas diversas camadas
- sistemas heterogêneos de comunicação, de virtualização e de processamento
- flexibilidade para agregação de novos blocos funcionais e
- orquestração inteligente, baseada em técnicas de aprendizado de máquina

4

Fig. 16.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Objetivos Gerais

Objetivo 2

Demonstrar a viabilidade da arquitetura PORVIR-5G em diversos **casos de uso**, explorando **requisitos avançados** das redes 5G, especialmente em termos de:

- latência
- confiabilidade
- cobertura
- mobilidade e
- banda

5

Fig. 17.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Fatiamento e programabilidade nas redes 5G

Fig. 18.

-- > ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:

Desafios e meios

Desafios no gerenciamento de fatiamento de redes

- Proposição de uma arquitetura de suporte ao conceito de Slice-as-a-Service
 - UNISINOS, UFRGS, UNICAMP, UFMG
- Avaliação da arquitetura de Slice-as-a-Service para compartilhamento em redes 5G
 - UNISINOS, UFRGS, UNICAMP, UFMG

Fig. 19.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Desafios e meios

Desafios na orquestração de redes 5G

- Proposição de um modelo para orquestração de funções de rede virtualizadas
 - UFES, UNISINOS, UFRGS, UFMG
- Identificação de violações na QoE a partir do desempenho da rede
 - UFES, UNISINOS, UFRGS, UFMG
- Escolha do melhor parâmetro para atuar em uma rede multidomínio
 - UNISINOS, UFRGS, UFMG
- Atuação em redes multiaplicação
 - UNISINOS, UFRGS, UFMG

Grings, F., et al., Orquestração dinâmica total de fatiamento de rede no núcleo 5G sobre plataformas nativas de computação em nuvem

Fig. 20.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Desafios e meios

Desafios em programabilidade de redes

- Investigação da programabilidade do sistema numérico de resíduos como um conceito fundamental para arquiteturas de rede 5G programáveis
 - UFES, UNICAMP
- Extensão das interfaces SDN
 - UFMG, UFES, UNICAMP

Fig. 21.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Programabilidade de resíduos polinomiais (PolKA)

Fig. 22.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Programabilidade de redes

Run-time Adaptive In-Kernel BPF/XDP Solution for 5G UPF

- Extensão das interfaces SDN via implementação de planos de dados para arquiteturas de rede 5G programáveis
- Repositório público: <https://github.com/navarrothiago/upf-bpf>

Fig. 23.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Desafios e meios

Comunicação massiva máquina-a-máquina: aplicação de Internet das Coisas - IoT

- Implementar modelo de comunicação mMTC na plataforma PORVIR-5G para otimização de IoTs
- Avaliar modelo de comunicação mMTC demonstrando uma variedade de aplicações de IoT inteligentes
 - UNISINOS, UFRGS

Caso de uso em otimização de redes LPWAN sensível ao contexto para redes militares táticas

Context-aware environment monitoring to support LPWAN-based battlefield applications 12
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comcom.2022.02.020>

Fig. 24.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Demonstrações

Fig. 25.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Demonstrações

Comunicações ultra-confiáveis e de baixa latência: drones

- Implementar e avaliar modelos de comunicação URLLC em drones na plataforma PORVIR-5G

Comunicação massiva máquina-a-máquina: aplicação de Internet das Coisas

- Implementar e avaliar modelos de comunicação mMTC na plataforma PORVIR-5G para uma variedade de aplicações de IoT inteligentes

Banda Larga Móvel: vídeo de alta definição

- Implementar e avaliar modelos de comunicação eMBB na plataforma PORVIR-5G para transmissão de vídeo de alta definição

Fig. 26.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Futuro das pesquisa experimental

A área de redes e telecomunicações não é mais atrativa como antigamente?

- A indústria de telecom está vivendo uma grande transformação decorrentes da desagregação horizontal e vertical e as iniciativas *open source*
- Avançar nas redes comunitárias (Redecomep) usando antenas 5G nas universidades e PORVIR-5G como habilitador
- As infraestruturas 6G baseadas em software e serviços serão orgânicas e altamente dinâmicas
- Arquitetura baseada em redes abertas (O-RAN)
- Estendendo a integração de redes não terrestres (NTN)
- Integrando novas tecnologias disruptivas, como Terahertz e comunicações quântica
- Avanços na disponibilidade de dados para serem utilizados em Inteligência Artificial para automatização das redes

15

Fig. 27.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

Fig. 28.

-- > **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION:**

SFI2 - Slicing Future Internet Infrastructures

MULTIINSTITUTIONAL COLLABORATIVE RESEARCH PROJECT

Fig. 29.

-- > **SFI2 INSTITUTIONS:**

Fig. 30.

-- > **SFI2 FUNDING:**

SFI2 Project is funded by FAPESP - Project 2018/23097-3

Fig. 31.

-- > **SFI2 SUPPORT:**

RNP - Brazilian Educational and Research Network
FIBRE Network - Future Internet Brazilian Environment for Experimentation

REFERENCES

- [1] Antonio Abelem, Michael Stanton, Iara Machado, Marcos Salvador, Luiz Magalhaes, Natalia Fernandes, Sand Correa, Kleber Cardoso, Cesar Marcondes, Joberto Martins, Jose Monteiro, Tereza Carvalho, and José Rezende. FIT@ BR - A Future Internet Testbed in Brazil. In *Proceedings of the APAN – Network Research Workshop*, pages 1–8, 2013.
- [2] Cristiano Both, Rafael Guimaraes, Frank Slyne, Juliano Wickboldt, Magnos Martinello, Cristina Dominicini, Rafael Martins, Yi Zhang, Diego Cardoso, Rodolfo Villaca, Isabella Ceravolo, Reza Nejabati, Johann Marquez-Barja, Marco Ruffini, and Luiz DaSilva. FUTEBOL Control Framework: Enabling Experimentation in Convergent Optical, Wireless, and Cloud Infrastructures. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 57(10):56–62, October 2019.
- [3] Aloizio P. Silva, Christos Tranoris, Spyros Denazis, Susana Sargento, João Pereira, Miguel Luís, Rodrigo Moreira, Flávio Silva, Ivan Vidal, Borja Nogales, Reza Nejabati, and Dimitra Simeonidou. 5GInfire: An End-to-End Open5G Vertical Network Function Ecosystem. *Ad Hoc Networks*, 93:101895, October 2019.
- [4] Stuart Clayman, Augusto Neto, Fábio Verdi, Sand Correa, Silvio Sampaio, Ilias Sakelariou, Letteris Mamatias, Rafael Pasquini, Kleber Cardoso, Francesco Tusa, Christian Rothenberg, and Joan Serrat. The NECOS Approach to End-to-End Cloud-Network Slicing as a Service. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 59(3):91–97, March 2021. Conference Name: IEEE Communications Magazine.
- [5] Gustavo Neves Dias, José Ferreira Rezende, Leandro Neumann Ciuffo, Iara Machado, Flavio de Oliveira Silva, Tereza Cristina de Brito, Fernando Frota Redigolo, Joberto S. B. Martins, Leobino N. Sampaio, and Antonio Jorge Gomes Abelem. SFI2 - Slicing Future Internet Infrastructures project. In *Proceedings of the The Global Experimentation for Future Internet (GEFI)*, pages 1–3, Coimbra, Portugal, November 2019.
- [6] Flávio de Oliveira Silva, Tereza Cristina Carvalho, Joberto S. B. Martins, Cristiano Bonato Both, and Daniel Fernandes Macedo. Slicing Future Internet Infrastructures Round Table. Technical Report TR01/2021, Universidade de São Paulo (USP), São Paulo, Brazil, 2021.

Prof. Dr. Armando Nolasco Pinto - Armando Nolasco Pinto received the Graduation degree in Electronic and Telecommunications Engineering, in 1994, and received the Ph.D. degree in Electrical Engineering in 1999, both from the University of Aveiro. He joined the Institute of Telecommunications, as a Researcher in the Optical Communications and Photonics Group, and the Electronic, Telecommunications, and Informatics Department of the University of Aveiro, as a Lecturer, in 1995 and 1997, respectively. He is currently an Associate Professor at the Department of Electronic, Telecommunications, and Informatics, University of Aveiro and leads the Optical Communications and Photonics Group at the Aveiro site of the Institute of Telecommunications. His research interests include high-speed optical communication systems and networks. He has authored or co-authored more than 100 scientific papers in international journals and conferences. Dr. Pinto is a Senior member of the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), a member of the Optical Society of America (OSA), and a member of the International Society for Optics and Photonics (SPIE).

Prof. Dr. Nuno Alexandre Peixoto Silva - Nuno Silva received a degree in Physics from the University of Minho, Braga, Portugal, and a master's degree in Physics from the University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal, in 2006 and 2008, respectively. He received his Ph.D. in Electrical Engineering at Aveiro University for research in quantum cryptography in optical-fiber communication systems in 2013. Since 2019, is an Auxiliary Researcher at Instituto de Telecomunicações where he is developing expertise in the field of quantum cryptography as a resource for secure multiparty computation. He is actively participating in several RD projects. He teaches courses related to quantum optics and technologies at the Physics Department of the University of Aveiro. Currently, he is a researcher with the Optical Quantum Communications and Technologies Group. His current research interests include Optical Communications; Nonlinear Classical Optics; Optical Detection; Information Theory; Secure Multiparty Computation; Quantum Effects in Optical Waveguides; Single and Entangled Photonic States Generation and Detection; Practical Quantum Cryptography; Quantum Key Distribution, Quantum Bit Commitment, Quantum Oblivious Transfer; Quantum Oblivious Key Distribution; Quantum Homodyne and Heterodyne Detection. Nuno Silva is a Member of the Editorial Board of the Applied Sciences Journal as Topic Editor. He is also a Member of the Editorial Board of the section Optics and Lasers in Applied Sciences Journal. Currently, he is also Guest Editor of the Special Issue "Advances in Photonic Technologies and Cryptographic Applications" at Applied Sciences Journal.

Profa. Dra. Tereza Cristina de Brito Carvalho - Associate Professor of Escola Politécnica – University of São Paulo (USP) and visiting professor at Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne. She is founder and general coordinator of LASSU (Laboratory of Sustainability on ITC) since 2010 and CEDIR-USP (Center for Reuse and Discard of Informatics Residuals) since 2009. She is former assessor of CTI – USP (Information Technology Coordination) during 2010-2013 and director of CCE-USP (Electronic Computing Center) during 2006-2010. She is Sloan Fellow 2002 from MIT (Massachusetts Institute of Technology). She has coordinated international and national R&D projects since 2000 in: Green Computing, Cloud Computing, IT Energy Efficiency, IT Governance, Digital Technologies applied to the Amazon Production Chains, WEEE (Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment), Future Internet, Scientific DMZ and Security. She holds several international patents.

Prof. Dr. Joberto S. B. Martins - Professor at Salvador University (UNIFACS) and PhD in Computer Science at Université Pierre et Marie Curie - UPMC, Paris (1986). Invited Professor at HTW - Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft des Saarlandes (Germany) since 2003, Senior Research Period at Université of Paris-Saclay in 2016, Salvador University head and researcher at NUPERC and IPQoS research groups on Resource Allocation Models, Software Defined Networking - OpenFlow, Smart Cities, Smart Grid, Cognitive Management and machine learning application. Previously worked as Invited Professor at Université Paris VI and Institut National des Télécommunications (INT) in France and as key speaker, teacher and invited lecturer in various international congresses and companies in Brazil, US and Europe.

Prof. Dr. Cristiano Bonato Both - Professor of the Applied Computing Graduate Program at the University of Vale do Rio dos Sinos (UNISINOS), Brazil. He is a research fellow of the Brazilian National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq). Cristiano has experience in coordinating several research projects funded by H2020 EU-Brazil, CNPq, FAPERGS, and RNP. His research focuses on wireless networks, Mobile technologies (RAN and 5GC), softwarization and virtualization technologies for telecommunication networks, and SDN-like solutions for IoT Low-Power Wide Area Network (LPWAN). Currently, he is involved with research activities on wireless networks, signal processing, computer network architecture, and software-defined networking publishing his scientific works in journals with high impact factor, such as IEEE Communication Magazine, IEEE Wireless Communications, IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology, Computer

Networks Journal (Elsevier), etc. Moreover, Cristiano is participating in several Technical Programme and Organizing Committees for different worldwide conferences and congresses.

Prof. Dr. Antonio Jorge G. Abelém - He is full Professor in the Computer Science Faculty at the Federal University of Pará (UFPA). He holds a Ph.D. in Computer Science from the Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro (PUC-Rio, 2003). He is an associate and member of the Board of the Brazilian Computer Society (SBC). He coordinates the Research Laboratory in Computer Network and Multimedia Communication (GERCOM) from which participates and coordinates several national and international projects. He is a TPC member and reviewer of national and international conferences and journals. His research is focused on future internet, software-defined networking, network function virtualization, internet of things, performance analysis, and network security. In 2020, he was visiting professor at the University of Massachusetts (UMass), in Amherst-MA, where he carried out research on quantum networks